

The Evolution of Economic Terms in Terms of the Degree of Adaptation

Muhayyo Qutliyeva ¹

¹ Independent researcher of Bukh.S.U.

Abstract:

This article discusses the substantial technological and scientific revolutions, the reconstruction of the global socioeconomic and political landscape, and the unprecedented acceleration of the study of worldwide languages throughout the 20th century, particularly in its second half.

In the context of lexical-semantic, phonetic, and grammatical adaptation, the functional link between economic terms and their distinctive features are examined.

Keywords: economy, society, economic terms, lexicographic resources.

Introduction. It is known that the economy plays an important role in any society. Therefore, words and terms related to economics should be clear, concise and logically based. The rapid development of science and technology affects the economy, as a result of which new neologisms appear in this field. Thanks to globalization, it is important and necessary to develop an internationally accepted terminological fund in the field of economy in the Uzbek language, to create lexicographic resources containing quality translations of economic terms. Economic terms are crucial in the modern world because they are used to describe the complex systems and concepts that form the basis of the global economy. English is the dominant language in international trade and commerce, but many other languages are also spoken in the world, including Uzbek. There is no doubt that the economic sphere of both countries is constantly evolving, changing its form and content. Therefore, it leads to frequent changes in the lexicon that serve the verbal communication between representatives of the economic sphere. In the modern world, the translation of economic terms is in high demand due to the development of the digital economy, banking, marketing, organizational management, and international trade. Any translator can translate an economic text or term, but the meaning is often incorrect due to a lack of economic knowledge. To translate economic terms from English into Uzbek, you need to have both linguistic and economic

knowledge, and translating terms and texts without a deep knowledge of economics and the peculiarities of its use in a particular country is not enough.

As we study economic terms in English and Uzbek, it becomes clear that many economic terms are formed in different ways. Many of the terms are derived from the Uzbek language. A group of ready-made alternative terms in Uzbek language will be formed, and some of them will be translated and used in speech, and some will be recreated based on the laws of the Uzbek language. Another method is the assimilation of international terms into Uzbek. It should be noted that it is difficult to find an Uzbek alternative to all these terms. So most of them are actually used, and this application is universal, and it's very useful for business people to share information. For instance: *corruption - korrupsiya, credit - kredit, export - eksport, grant - grant, auditor - auditor, leasing - lizing, manager - menedjer, license - litsenziya, businessman - biznesmen, non-resident - norezident.*

English and Uzbek have adopted many economic terms into English from other languages, particularly French and German. 65 economic terms have been adopted from Persian, Turkish, and Russian into Uzbek. Some words in the field of economics do not undergo any changes in translation. For example, the term “*inflation*” is derived from the French word “*inflation*”, and the term “*deflation*” is derived from the Latin word “*deflation*”. Similarly, the Uzbek language has borrowed many economic terms from the Russian language, which has a strong influence on the Uzbek language for historical reasons. According to the vocabulary, many economic terms are similar in English and Uzbek. For example, the word “*budget*” is “*byudjet*” in Uzbek, while the word “*investment*” is “*investment*” in both languages.

Referring to modern technologies in the translation of texts is one of the main directions of today's modern translation studies. Translation should be considered as both a linguistic and cultural process. Translation, of course, is not just a linguistic movement; it is also an act of cultural, cultural communication. Translation always involves two languages and two cultures, as the two cannot be separated from each other. It is very important to include specific nuances of any culture in translation.

Example, the terms “Bull and Bear” are used to describe market conditions in an economy. The translation of “Bull” is “ox” (ho’kiz) in Uzbek, an economic term used in English as “bull market”. In addition, the bull market is a growing economy and a highly employed market. As a result of the steady growth of the company's stock price, strong supply and weak supply for securities are important in the “bull market”. Investors participate in the hope of profit and compete for capital in the “bull market”.

The creators of special dictionaries and reference books on economics in their publications “each term discussed in the publication is distinguished by its English analogue”. Thus, practical materials confirm that foreign language supplements are not borrowing (assimilation) in pure form. Foreign language adverbs (transplanted adverbs) can freeze for a long time at the initial stage.

1. The first stage (direct input, penetration) is transliteration or trans-phonation. This stage of word acquisition involves a certain connection with the graphics of the Russian language, and the orthographic aspect is ignored.
2. Use in function and speech is characterized by irregular, unsystematic accumulation (utilization) of borrowed words. At this stage, paradigmatic connections appear: polysemy, synonymy, anatomy.
3. Lexicographic processing, regulation of new borrowed words.

The inclusion of the word in the grammatical system, its connection with gender, number forms and type of declension requires the need to harmonize new borrowed words with the spelling rules of

the Russian language in a certain way. Adverbs, like foreign citizens abroad, must obey the laws of the country where they are located.

4. Use of terms included in the dictionary, taking into account the norms of the modern Uzbek literary language. At this stage, a change in the original semantic meaning of a word borrowed from a foreign language occurs, a loss of genre-stylistic, situational and social features of borrowing in a new language environment. The terms “Establishment” and “publicity” are used only to refer to US and English society, usually with negative connotations. Currently, these terms are used in a neutral sense, like other words denoting the realities of the capitalist system: business, manager, and dealer. In the field of terminology, the widespread use of the term and its social importance lead to the expansion of its original specialized meaning. Some researchers call this phenomenon “determinology”, but the term does not lose its narrow professional meaning in its terminological field.

The final stage of mastering is to record it in the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language. Lexicologists argue that interpretative dictionaries generally interpret word meaning more fully than highly specialized dictionaries because annotated dictionaries give all the meanings of a word: direct, figurative, and highly specialized.

The word is recorded in an explanatory dictionary with derivatives, its partial speech affiliation and grammatical categories are indicated. Each acquired word strictly goes through all stages of adaptation. The process of adaptation of borrowed words includes several stages at the same time; they intersect and complement each other, speeding up the assimilation process. For example, modified possessive words (suffix) combine elements of transliteration or trans-phonation: in the process of assimilation, suffixation implies connection with the grammatical system of the Russian language, semantic adaptation through word-forming affixes.

The structural types of one-word terms analyzed as following:

- 1) term - simple word;
- 2) term - complex word;
- 3) term - compound word.

Joint names of the undivided type include a very large group of acquisitions that show regularity characteristics such as time-sheet (тайм-шит), demise-charter (димайз-чартер).

A lexicon can be formed from such names: time-sheet, time-charter, time-out, charter, bareboat-charter, dimes-charter, bank, bank-dealer, bank-issuer, bank-guarantor, bank-acceptant.

Some terms are not yet defined structurally, and they occur in several variants: as a compound word {off-shore, roll-over} and as a simple (simplified) word {offshore, rollover}, as a term simple word (freelongside), as a compound term (freelongside), as a phrase (free-long-side), and as an abbreviation (FLS).

Abbreviations come from a single source, usually a phrase that has a terminological meaning and, moreover, a social significance.

A contraction is a combination of abbreviations and full words: caption, (cap + option) LIBOR (the index of interbank deposit rates in the London financial market), MIS - like the financial sector.

As a result of comparative analysis, we found that the structure of compound words in English – Uzbek is not homogeneous. Complex marketing terms in English are compact, and in most cases they correspond to phrases (automaker - car company, brainstorming - brainstorming), very rarely they are translated into Russian through single-word components (bangtail – „dum“, offshore ” – “behind the sea”). In some cases, they are not equivalent in the recipient language, and a descriptive

translation of the terms is used (keystoning - retail pricing by automatically doubling the wholesale price).

Also, when new terms are formed, conversion occurs, that is, the method of word formation that passes from one part of speech to another. Words do not change their spelling and sound, but change their meaning.

Conclusion

As a result of this method of word formation, the language acquires morphological freedom, because the same word is used as different parts of a sentence, thereby performing a different syntactic function (that is, having different parts of a sentence). In English marketing terminology, conversion is one of the ways to form new terms, that is, to move from one part of speech to another.

Thus, the composition of financial and economic terms in the English language and their derivative features are diverse. They reflect the specifics of the direction, both in English and in the interdisciplinary plan. Therefore, many terms of the English language work in two ways in the field of marketing based on materials in other languages (in our case, Russian and Uzbek) according to their meaning and word formation characteristics:

- 1) unchanged;
- 2) with a change in spelling, pronunciation, with synonyms in the receiving language and without synonyms.

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